

ABSTRACT BOOK

**International Congress on Nuclear Medicine,
Molecular Imaging and Molecular Therapy**
FROM IMAGE TO DIAGNOSIS & TREATMENT
Novi Sad April 19-20, 2024

Organizers:

Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad
&
Academy of Medical Sciences Serbian Medical Society

Organizing Committee

Prof Jasna Mihailović, MD, PhD

Department of Nuclear Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad,
Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

Assoc Prof Nataša Prvulović-Bunović, MD, PhD

Department of Nuclear Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad,
Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

Dr Jelena Roganović, MD

Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

Scientific Committee

Prof Stanley Goldsmith, MD, ScD (Hon), DMed (Hon)

Professor Emeritus in Radiology,
Professor of Medicine, Weill Cornell Medicine, New York City, USA

Prof Leonard Freeman, MD

Professor Emeritus, Montefiore Medical Center,
Albert Einstein College of Medicine, New York City, New York, USA

Prof Douglas Van Nostrand, MD

Professor of Medicine, Georgetown University School of Medicine,
Washington, USA

Prof Lisa Bodei, MD, PhD

Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center, New York City, USA

Prof Ralph McCready, MD, PhD

Hon Consultant Nuclear Medicine, Royal Sussex County
Hospital Brighton, Brighton, UK

Prof Sonya Sergieva, MD, PhD

Sofia Cancer Center Sofia, Department of Nuclear Medicine, Sofia, Bulgaria

Prof. Zvezdana Rajkovača, MD, PhD

Department of Nuclear Medicine and Thyroid Gland Disease,
University Clinical Centre of the Republic of Srpska,
Faculty of Medicine Banja Luka,
Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Prof. Venjamin Majstorov, MD, PhD

Medical Faculty, Institute of Pathophysiology and Nuclear Medicine,
Skopje, North Macedonia

Prof Vladimir Obradović, MD, PhD
Head of Board of Directors, Clinical Centre of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia

Prof Milovan Matović, MD, PhD
Polyclinic Joković, Kragujevac, Serbia

Prof Marina Vlajković, MD, PhD
Center of Nuclear Medicine, University Clinical Center Niš,
Faculty of Medicine, University of Niš, Niš, Serbia

Prof Vera Artiko, MD, PhD
Center for Nuclear Medicine with Positron Emission Tomography,
University Clinical Center of Serbia,
Faculty of Medicine University of Belgrade, Serbia

Prof Dragana Šobić Šaranović, MD, PhD
Center for Nuclear Medicine with Positron Emission Tomography,
University Clinical Center of Serbia,
Faculty of Medicine University of Belgrade, Serbia

Ass Prof. Dragan Pucar, MD, PhD
Institute for Nuclear Medicine, Military Medical Academy, Belgrade, Serbia

Dr Aleksandar Simić, MD
Special Hospital for Thyroid Gland and Metabolism Diseases Zlatibor, Serbia

Research Prof Sanja Vranješ-Đurić, PhD
Institute of Nuclear Science, Vinča, Serbia

A CASE REPORT OF ADENOMA OF THE PARATHYROID GLAND

Bazic Đorović B.¹, Popović Krneta M.¹, Stanoevski M.¹, Vuksanović A.¹,
Pantović J.², Nedeljković S.³, Mijatović Teodorović Lj.^{1,4}

¹Department of Nuclear Medicine, Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia

²Center for Nuclear Medicine with PET, University Clinical Center of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia

³Institute of Nuclear Medicine, Military Medical Academy, Belgrade, Serbia

⁴University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Medical Sciences, Kragujevac, Serbia

Introduction: Preoperative planar Tc-99m-sestamibi scintigraphy, complemented by SPECT/CT (Single-Photon Emission Computed Tomography with Computed Tomography) imaging of the neck and chest, offers higher sensitivity in detecting hyperfunctioning parathyroid glands, facilitating successful parathyroidectomy. **Case report:** We present a case of a 33-year-old female patient who had been diagnosed with tumor measuring 9x22x55 mm (APxLLxKK), located between the right lobe of the thyroid gland and the common carotid artery on neck CT, initially suspected to be an aberrant blood vessel. Subsequent neck MRI (*Magnetic Resonance Imaging*) confirmed the tumor. The laboratory analyses showed an increase in following parameters: PTH 310 (up to 68) and Ca 2.92 (up to 2.55) with a normal vitamin D. Due to that the patient was referred for scintigraphy of the parathyroid glands, which was performed in another institution, and scintigraphy yielded negative results. For further evaluation of the disease, the patient was referred to the Institute of Oncology and Radiology of Serbia, where the repeat scintigraphy was done but with SPECT/CT. SPECT/CT examination revealed a hypodense soft tissue mass measuring 9x22x50mm (APxLLxKK), which was located between the right thyroid lobe, common carotid artery and jugular veins. The described mass intensively accumulates the radiopharmaceutical and corresponds to the hyperfunctionally altered right parathyroid gland. The suspected hyperfunctional parathyroid gland was surgically removed, confirmed to be an adenoma. After the operation a decrease in value of the PTH was registered. **Conclusion:** This case emphasizes the significance of Tc-99m-sestamibi planar scintigraphy coupled with additional SPECT/CT imaging of the neck for accurate identification of parathyroid glands and subsequent treatment planning.

Keywords: Parathyroid Gland, Adenoma, Tc-99m-Sestamibi SPECT/CT